

A Bayesian Semiparametric Approach to Conditional Survival Estimation for Heavy-Tailed Data Under Right-Censoring

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Abstract

This study explores estimation of conditional survival functions for heavy-tailed right-censored data, a recurring problem in medical and applied research. We develop a Bayesian semiparametric model based on a finite stick-breaking mixture of Amoroso bulk components with component-specific generalized Pareto tails, enabling robust inference for survival, conditional survival, and hazard functions within a unified framework. The approach accommodates random right censoring, covariate information, and flexible upper-tail behavior through ordered component-specific thresholds. Simulation studies and a real-data application demonstrate improved stability and accuracy relative to standard benchmark models, especially in sparsely observed tail regions.

Keywords *Bayesian Nonparametric, Dirichlet process mixture, Extreme value theory, Generalized Pareto distribution, Right censoring, Survival function*

1 Introduction

Estimating conditional survival under right-censoring and heavy-tailed outcome distributions is a central challenge in medical and applied statistical research. In clinical settings such as heart transplantation or oncology, long-term survival estimation conditional on individual characteristics (e.g., age, comorbidities, or biomarker levels) is essential for informing prognosis, guiding treatment decisions, and facilitating patient communication.

The standard survival function is defined as:

$$S(t | X = x) = \Pr(T > t | X = x), \quad (1)$$

where T denotes survival time and X represents baseline covariates. However, this unconditional formulation does not account for patients who have already survived to a certain time point. A more clinically relevant quantity is the conditional survival function, which updates the survival probability given survival up to a certain time s :

$$CS(t | s, x) = \Pr(T > t + s | T > s, X = x) = \frac{S(t + s | X = x)}{S(s | X = x)}. \quad (2)$$

This conditional perspective enables dynamic survival updating and has shown clinical value in contexts where early survival is strongly associated with future risk. For example, in oncology, conditional survival offers more realistic estimates for patients who have survived high-risk initial periods [Karrison, 1987, Holford et al., 2019]. Methodologically, Bayesian approaches targeting conditional survival directly have also been developed [Zhou and Hanson, 2018].

Reliable estimation of conditional survival functions, particularly in the long term, requires accurate modeling across both the central body and the tail of the survival distribution. Semiparametric models such as the Cox proportional hazards model [Cox, 1972] are widely used due to their interpretability and robustness. However, they may perform poorly in the distributional extremes, where right-censoring is prevalent and data are sparse, precisely where conditional survival estimation is often most needed.

To address tail instability, Extreme Value Theory (EVT) offers a principled framework. For observations exceeding a high threshold, the Generalized Pareto Distribution (GPD) provides a well-established limiting model [Pickands III, 1975], with comprehensive overviews in [Coles, 2001, Embrechts et al., 1997]. EVT has been extended to censored survival data [Stupfler, 2016], and Bayesian approaches for estimating tail parameters under censoring have been proposed [Ameraoui et al., 2016]. Recent studies also compare GPD parameter estimation strategies in practice [Gómez-Déniz et al., 2022], and likelihood-based tail index inference has been theoretically characterized [Drees et al., 2004].

Complementarily, Bayesian nonparametric models, particularly Dirichlet process mixtures, offer flexibility in modeling the central region of the survival distribution. These models support multimodal densities, non-monotonic hazard rates, and natural incorporation of censoring, with efficient computation enabled via stick-breaking constructions [Sethuraman, 1994]. We adopt the four-parameter Amoroso distribution as the mixture kernel, a flexible family encompassing more than 30 lifetime distributions [Crooks, 2010] and capable of capturing skewness and heavy-tailed behavior. Prior work has explored hybrid strategies that splice a flexible model for the central region with an EVT-based tail for extreme quantile estimation [do Nascimento et al., 2012]. We extend this idea to target conditional survival directly in a Bayesian framework.

In this paper, we propose a unified semi-parametric Bayesian model for estimating conditional survival probability (3) under heavy-tailed, right-censored data. Computation is based on a truncated stick-breaking mixture of Amoroso kernels, with each component spliced to its own generalized Pareto tail through an ordered subject-specific threshold. This construction enables adaptivity to complex survival patterns while preserving principled tail extrapolation. The induced hazard can be non-monotone despite monotone component hazards (see Supplementary Section 7.1), and covariate effects enter both the bulk and tail portions of the model.

The central innovation lies in directly modeling the conditional survival function as the target of inference. By addressing censoring, covariate dependence, and tail behavior within a unified framework, our method yields dynamically updated, stable survival estimates across the entire time horizon. This approach is particularly valuable in clinical prognosis, where survival expectations evolve meaningfully as patients surpass early high-risk periods [Karrison, 1987].

2 Methodology

We begin with a set of n independent observations, denoted by $\{Y_i, \delta_i, X_i\}_{i \leq n}$ with

$$Y_i = \min(T_i, C_i), \quad \delta_i = \mathbb{I}\{T_i \leq C_i\} \quad \forall i \leq n.$$

Each Y_i represents the observed time, where T_i is the true event time and C_i is the censoring time. The binary indicator δ_i records whether the event was observed(1) or censored(0). Each subject is also associated with a covariate vector $X_i \in \mathbb{R}^p$. To maintain brevity, we will omit the subject indicator i and reintroduce it in Section 3.1.

Our initial inferential target is the survival function given covariate, which expresses the probability that an individual with covariates x survives beyond time t . The main interest of this essay lies in an alternative version of the conditional survival function mentioned in (2), which is given as:

$$CS(t_2 | t_1, x) = \Pr(T > t_2 | T > t_1, X = x) = \frac{S(t_2 | x)}{S(t_1 | x)} \quad \text{with } t_2 > t_1 \quad (3)$$

The representations in (2) and (3) are essentially the same quantity under the identification $t = t_1$ and $s = t_2 - t_1$. The former quantity describes the probability of surviving beyond the initial period, while the latter calculates the probability of surviving an additional time beyond the initial period. This CS function in (3) allows us to refine survival predictions as new survival milestones are reached, making it especially relevant in clinical contexts such as long-term prognosis following surgery, treatment, or diagnosis.

2.1 Assumptions

The implementation used in this article relies on the following assumptions.

- (A1) **Independent censoring:** The event time T is conditionally independent of the censoring time C given covariates X .
- (A2) **Component-wise thresholding:** Within each mixture component there exists a sufficiently high threshold beyond which exceedances can be represented by a generalized Pareto tail, consistent with peak-over-threshold modeling [Pickands III, 1975, de Haan and Ferreira, 2007].
- (A3) **Finite truncation for computation:** Posterior computation uses a finite stick-breaking truncation. In all reported analyses the truncation level is fixed at $m = 5$ components.

The first assumption is the standard identifiability condition for right-censored survival data. The second assumption is imposed on the event-time model rather than on the censoring model: the current implementation does not require censoring times to share the same tail index or domain-of-attraction as the event-time distribution. The third assumption is computational and reflects the exact NIMBLE implementation used throughout the paper.

2.2 Model Description

In this section, we aim to model the conditional density of observed times ($y \in \mathbb{R}^+$) given covariates, denoted $f(y | \mathbf{x})$, where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^p$ represents subject-specific covariates. Throughout the article vectors and matrices are denoted in boldface. The conditional density, cumulative distribution, and survival functions are related by

$$F(y | \mathbf{x}) = \int_0^y f(t | \mathbf{x}) dt \quad \text{and} \quad S(y | \mathbf{x}) = 1 - F(y | \mathbf{x}).$$

To accommodate distinct dynamics in the body and tail of the distribution, we use a finite stick-breaking mixture of spliced component densities. In the reported analyses the truncation level is fixed at $m = 5$. Let v_1, \dots, v_{m-1} denote the stick-breaking variables and define

$$w_1 = v_1, \quad w_j = v_j \prod_{\ell < j} (1 - v_\ell) \quad (j = 2, \dots, m-1), \quad w_m = \prod_{\ell=1}^{m-1} (1 - v_\ell),$$

so that $\sum_{j=1}^m w_j = 1$.

For component j , the bulk distribution is Amoroso with location μ_j , covariate-dependent bulk scale

$$\eta_{1ij} = \exp(\mathbf{x}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_j^{(1)}),$$

and shape parameters (α_j, γ_j) . The same component has a GPD tail with scale

$$\eta_{2ij} = \exp(\mathbf{x}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_j^{(2)})$$

and shape parameter ξ_j . The fitted NIMBLE model uses ordered component-specific thresholds. Writing u_t for the baseline empirical threshold, we define positive latent increments $z_{ij} > 0$ and set

$$u_{i1} = u_t + z_{i1}, \quad u_{ij} = u_{i,j-1} + z_{ij}, \quad j = 2, \dots, m.$$

In the implementation the increments z_{ij} are assigned lognormal regressions, which guarantees ordered thresholds for every subject.

$$f_A(y | \mu, \eta, \alpha, \gamma) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left| \frac{\gamma}{\eta} \right| \left(\frac{y - \mu}{\eta} \right)^{\alpha\gamma - 1} \exp \left[- \left(\frac{y - \mu}{\eta} \right)^\gamma \right], \quad (4)$$

with support $[\mu, \infty)$ when $\eta > 0$. In this paper we restrict attention to $\eta > 0$. The corresponding cumulative and survival functions are

$$F_A(y | \mu, \eta, \alpha, \gamma) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \gamma\left(\alpha, \left(\frac{y - \mu}{\eta}\right)^\gamma\right), \quad (5)$$

$$S_A(y | \mu, \eta, \alpha, \gamma) = 1 - F_A(y | \mu, \eta, \alpha, \gamma), \quad (6)$$

where $\gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$ denotes the lower incomplete Gamma function.

For $y \geq u$, the GPD density, survival function, and hazard are

$$f_{\text{GPD}}(y | u, \eta_2, \xi) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\eta_2} \left(1 + \frac{\xi(y - u)}{\eta_2}\right)^{-(1/\xi+1)}, & \xi \neq 0, \\ \frac{1}{\eta_2} \exp\left(-\frac{y - u}{\eta_2}\right), & \xi = 0, \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$S_{\text{GPD}}(y | u, \eta_2, \xi) = \begin{cases} \left(1 + \frac{\xi(y - u)}{\eta_2}\right)^{-1/\xi}, & \xi \neq 0, \\ \exp\left(-\frac{y - u}{\eta_2}\right), & \xi = 0, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$\lambda_{\text{GPD}}(y | u, \eta_2, \xi) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\eta_2} \left(1 + \frac{\xi(y - u)}{\eta_2}\right)^{-1}, & \xi \neq 0, \\ \frac{1}{\eta_2}, & \xi = 0. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

A positive ξ implies a heavy tail with infinite endpoint, $\xi = 0$ corresponds to exponential decay, and $\xi < 0$ implies a finite upper endpoint.

For component j , the spliced density is

$$f_j(y_i | \mathbf{x}_i, u_{ij}) = \begin{cases} f_A(y_i | \mu_j, \eta_{1ij}, \alpha_j, \gamma_j), & y_i < u_{ij}, \\ S_A(u_{ij} | \mu_j, \eta_{1ij}, \alpha_j, \gamma_j) f_{\text{GPD}}(y_i | u_{ij}, \eta_{2ij}, \xi_j), & y_i \geq u_{ij}. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The overall conditional density is

$$f(y_i | \mathbf{x}_i; \Theta) = \sum_{j=1}^m w_j f_j(y_i | \mathbf{x}_i, u_{ij}), \quad (11)$$

where Θ collects the mixture weights, bulk parameters, tail parameters, and ordered thresholds.

The corresponding survival function is

$$S(y_i | \mathbf{x}_i; \Theta) = \sum_{j=1}^m w_j S_j(y_i | \mathbf{x}_i, u_{ij}), \quad (12)$$

$$S_j(y_i | \mathbf{x}_i, u_{ij}) = \begin{cases} S_A(y_i | \mu_j, \eta_{1ij}, \alpha_j, \gamma_j), & y_i < u_{ij}, \\ S_A(u_{ij} | \mu_j, \eta_{1ij}, \alpha_j, \gamma_j) S_{\text{GPD}}(y_i | u_{ij}, \eta_{2ij}, \xi_j), & y_i \geq u_{ij}. \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

The overall hazard is therefore

$$\lambda(y_i | \mathbf{x}_i; \Theta) = \frac{f(y_i | \mathbf{x}_i; \Theta)}{S(y_i | \mathbf{x}_i; \Theta)}. \quad (14)$$

Because the model is a weighted sum of component-specific survival functions, the induced hazard can be non-monotone even when the component hazards are monotone; see Supplementary Section 7.1. We next describe the likelihood, implementation priors, and posterior computation used in the current code base.

3 Bayesian Hierarchical Models: Prior Specifications and Posterior Estimation

This section summarizes the likelihood and posterior computation used in the current implementation. The same structural model is used in simulation and application analyses, but some hyperparameters differ across those two workflows.

3.1 Likelihood Function and Prior Specification

Given observed data $D = \{y_i, \delta_i, \mathbf{x}_i\}_{i=1}^n$, the contribution of subject i is

$$L_i(\boldsymbol{\Theta} | D) = \left[f(y_i | \mathbf{x}_i; \boldsymbol{\Theta}) \right]^{\delta_i} \left[S(y_i | \mathbf{x}_i; \boldsymbol{\Theta}) \right]^{1-\delta_i},$$

where $f(\cdot)$ and $S(\cdot)$ are the full component-wise spliced density and survival functions defined in Section 2.2. The joint likelihood is

$$L(\boldsymbol{\Theta} | D) = \prod_{i=1}^n L_i(\boldsymbol{\Theta} | D),$$

and the posterior distribution satisfies

$$\Pr(\boldsymbol{\Theta} | D) \propto L(\boldsymbol{\Theta} | D) P_0(\boldsymbol{\Theta}),$$

where $P_0(\boldsymbol{\Theta})$ denotes the prior distribution.

The finite stick-breaking representation is common to both implementations:

$$v_j \sim \text{Beta}(1, \kappa), \quad \kappa \sim \text{Gamma}(1, 0.5), \quad j = 1, \dots, m-1.$$

Conditional on these variables, the weights are obtained deterministically through the stick-breaking construction above.

For the simulation study, the NIMBLE model in `Function/Sim.R` uses

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_j &\sim \text{Lognormal}(1, 2^2), & \alpha_j &\sim \text{Inv-Gamma}(3, 1), & \gamma_j &\sim \text{Inv-Gamma}(2, 1), \\ \beta_{kj}^{(1)} &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.25^2), & \beta_{kj}^{(2)} &\sim \mathcal{N}(0.3, 0.25^2), & \beta_{kj}^{(z)} &\sim \mathcal{N}(0.5, 0.3^2), \\ \xi_j &\sim \mathcal{N}(0.2, 0.1^2) \mathbb{I}(\xi_j > -0.5), & \text{var}_z &\sim \text{Inv-Gamma}(2, 1). \end{aligned}$$

For the MGUS application, the NIMBLE model in `Function/real_data_Sim.R` keeps the same stick-breaking prior, tail-shape prior, and var_z prior, but uses

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_j &\sim \text{Exp}(10), & \alpha_j &\sim \text{Inv-Gamma}(2, 1), & \gamma_j &\sim \text{Laplace}(1, 2), \\ \beta_{kj}^{(1)} &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.5^2), & \beta_{kj}^{(2)} &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.25^2), & \beta_{kj}^{(z)} &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, 2.5^2). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the paper reports one common structural model together with the exact hyperparameter settings used in each analysis pipeline.

3.2 Estimation and prediction of Survival and CS Probabilities

We obtain posterior draws $\{\boldsymbol{\Theta}^{(s)}\}_{s=1}^S$ from the fitted NIMBLE model. For a covariate profile \mathbf{x} and time t , the draw-specific survival probability is

$$S^{(s)}(t | \mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\Theta}^{(s)}) = \sum_{j=1}^m w_j^{(s)} S_j^{(s)}(t | \mathbf{x}, u_j^{(s)}(\mathbf{x})). \quad (15)$$

The posterior mean survival function is

$$\widehat{S}(t | \mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{s=1}^S S^{(s)}(t | \mathbf{x}; \Theta^{(s)}),$$

and reported credible intervals are obtained from the empirical quantiles of $\{S^{(s)}(t | \mathbf{x})\}_{s=1}^S$ at the nominal level used in the analysis.

For conditional survival, the draw-wise quantity is

$$CS^{(s)}(t_2 | t_1, \mathbf{x}; \Theta^{(s)}) = \frac{S^{(s)}(t_2 | \mathbf{x}; \Theta^{(s)})}{S^{(s)}(t_1 | \mathbf{x}; \Theta^{(s)})}, \quad t_2 > t_1, \quad (16)$$

with posterior mean

$$\widehat{CS}(t_2 | t_1, \mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{s=1}^S CS^{(s)}(t_2 | t_1, \mathbf{x}; \Theta^{(s)}).$$

In both the simulation and application pipelines, posterior survival probabilities are first computed on a prespecified covariate–time grid and conditional survival is then obtained by draw-wise ratios of adjacent or milestone-specific survival terms.

3.3 Comparative Models: Bayesian AFT and Bayesian PH

To benchmark the proposed model, we use the same two comparison procedures implemented in the current scripts.

The first comparator is a Bayesian Weibull accelerated failure time model fit with `brms`. For subject i ,

$$T_i | \mathbf{x}_i \sim \text{Weibull}(\kappa, \lambda_i), \quad \log \lambda_i = \mathbf{x}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{aft}}, \quad (17)$$

with right censoring handled through the `cens()` interface in `brms`. Posterior draws of $(\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{aft}}, \kappa)$ are converted to survival probabilities by the usual Weibull survival function

$$S_{\text{AFT}}(t | \mathbf{x}_i) = \exp\left[-\left\{t \exp(-\mathbf{x}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{aft}})\right\}^\kappa\right].$$

The second comparator is a Bayesian piecewise-exponential proportional-hazards model, also fit with `brms`. The survival data are first expanded with `survSplit` using the same empirical cut points that define the evaluation grid. Within interval $I_k = (t_{k-1}, t_k]$, the hazard is

$$h(t | \mathbf{x}_i) = \exp(\alpha_k + \mathbf{x}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{cox}}), \quad t \in I_k. \quad (18)$$

The resulting long-format likelihood is represented as a Poisson regression with interval fixed effects and an offset for exposure time. Posterior expected counts are converted to interval-specific hazard rates, cumulative hazards, and hence survival probabilities.

For both benchmark models, posterior survival summaries are computed on the same covariate–time grid used for the proposed method, and conditional survival is obtained from draw-wise survival ratios exactly as in Section 3.2. This keeps the comparison focused on model fit rather than on differing post-processing conventions.

4 Simulation Study

In this section, we implement our framework on synthetic datasets to evaluate our model’s performance and prediction accuracy across varying sample sizes. The results are compiled from multiple datasets, each containing observed timepoints Y , a censoring indicator δ , and subject-specific covariates \mathbf{x} for different sample sizes. The active simulation rerun set uses $n \in \{125, 250, 500, 750\}$. Representative summaries are shown in the main article, with additional results deferred to the supplementary materials.

4.1 Data Generation

The simulation generator in `Function/my_data_sim_censored.R` is a two-component spliced model with component-specific bulk and tail behavior. We generate

$$\mathbf{x}_i = (x_{1i}, x_{2i})^\top, \quad x_{1i} \sim \text{Uniform}(0, 1), \quad x_{2i} \sim \text{Uniform}(2, 4).$$

Let $C_i \in \{1, 2\}$ denote the component indicator with $\Pr(C_i = 1) = 0.6$ and $\Pr(C_i = 2) = 0.4$. The covariate-dependent bulk, threshold, and tail scales are

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_1(\mathbf{x}) &= \exp(0.9x_1 + 0.6x_2), & \eta_2(\mathbf{x}) &= \exp(0.4x_1 + 0.6x_2), \\ u_1(\mathbf{x}) &= \exp(0.55x_1 + 0.75x_2), & u_2(\mathbf{x}) &= \exp(0.70x_1 + 0.90x_2), \\ \eta_3(\mathbf{x}) &= \exp(0.35x_1 + 0.25x_2), & \eta_4(\mathbf{x}) &= \exp(0.30x_1 + 0.20x_2). \end{aligned}$$

Component 1 uses a shifted Gamma bulk with location $\mu_1 = 2$ and shape 1.25; component 2 uses a shifted Weibull bulk with location $\mu_2 = 3$ and shape 0.9. Their tail shapes are $\xi_1 = 0.25$ and $\xi_2 = 0.15$, respectively.

The event-time generator can be summarized as

$$\begin{aligned} C_i &\sim \text{Categorical}(0.6, 0.4), \\ B_i \mid (C_i = 1, \mathbf{x}_i) &\sim \text{ShiftedGamma}(\mu_1, 1.25, \eta_1(\mathbf{x}_i)), \\ B_i \mid (C_i = 2, \mathbf{x}_i) &\sim \text{ShiftedWeibull}(\mu_2, 0.9, \eta_2(\mathbf{x}_i)), \\ E_i \mid (C_i = 1, \mathbf{x}_i) &\sim \text{GPD}(u_1(\mathbf{x}_i), \eta_3(\mathbf{x}_i), 0.25), \\ E_i \mid (C_i = 2, \mathbf{x}_i) &\sim \text{GPD}(u_2(\mathbf{x}_i), \eta_4(\mathbf{x}_i), 0.15), \\ T_i &= \begin{cases} B_i, & U_i < F_{B_i}(u_{C_i}(\mathbf{x}_i) \mid \mathbf{x}_i), \\ E_i, & U_i \geq F_{B_i}(u_{C_i}(\mathbf{x}_i) \mid \mathbf{x}_i), \end{cases} \quad U_i \sim \text{Uniform}(0, 1). \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Thus each selected component is itself spliced at its own threshold, and the full event-time model is a mixture of those two spliced components.

Censoring times are generated from a GPD with shape 0.25, scale 10, and a replication-specific threshold equal to the 30th percentile of the generated bulk draw used in that replication. The observed data are

$$Y_i = \min(T_i, C_i^*), \quad \delta_i = \mathbb{I}(T_i < C_i^*),$$

with achieved censoring close to 30% on average.

For truth evaluation, the generator stores six empirical event-time quantiles in `new_Y`, corresponding to probabilities (0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 0.90, 0.95, 0.99). It also evaluates the true survival and conditional survival functions on the nine-point diagonal covariate grid

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j = \left(q_j, 2 + \frac{q_j - 0.1}{0.8} \right)^\top, \quad q_j \in \{0.1, 0.2, \dots, 0.9\},$$

yielding $9 \times 6 = 54$ covariate–time evaluation cells.

Figure 1: Heatmaps of survival and conditional survival across the nine-point diagonal covariate grid used by the simulation generator. **Panel A:** Survival probability at six time points corresponding to the 25th, 50th, 75th, 90th, 95th, and 99th percentiles of the true event-time distribution. Facet titles report the percentile and the corresponding time (rounded to two decimals). **Panel B:** Conditional survival on the same time grid. The first facet repeats survival at the earliest time point; the remaining five facets show the probability of surviving from one listed time point to the next, with facet titles reporting “current | previous” times (rounded to two decimals). A shared gray scale encodes probability from 0 to 1 (darker shades indicate higher probability).

For each active sample size $n \in \{125, 250, 500, 750\}$, the code generates one covariate matrix \mathbf{x} and then simulates $R = 100$ independent replications of event times and censoring indicators conditional on that same covariate design.

4.2 Simulation Setup and Accuracy Measures

For the proposed MixAmGPD approach described in Section 3.2, the NIMBLE model was fit with $m = 5$ mixture components, 3 chains, 6000 iterations per chain, 2000 burn-in iterations, and thinning by 3. The simulation script reports equal-tail 90% credible intervals for all three methods. Convergence was assessed through standard trace-plot diagnostics together with \widehat{R} and effective sample size summaries.

Predictive evaluation focused on the conditional survival function $CS(t_k | t_{k-1}, \mathbf{x})$ over the stored truth grid. The time points $\{t_k\}_{k=1}^6$ were the six empirical truth quantiles stored in `new_Y`. These correspond to the (0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 0.90, 0.95, 0.99) quantiles of the Monte Carlo event-time distribution. The covariate grid $\{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j\}_{j=1}^9$ was the diagonal grid defined in Section 4.1. Hence each method was compared over 54 covariate–time cells for every replication.

For each posterior draw $s = 1, \dots, S$, survival probabilities $S^{(s)}(t_k | \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)$ were computed using the model-specific survival functions in Equations (17), (18), and (15). The conditional survival probabilities were then obtained as

$$CS^{(s)}(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) = \frac{S^{(s)}(t_k | \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)}{S^{(s)}(t_{k-1} | \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)}, \quad (20)$$

and their posterior mean estimates were computed by averaging across posterior draws:

$$\widehat{CS}(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{s=1}^S CS^{(s)}(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j). \quad (21)$$

The resulting conditional survival surfaces, $\{\widehat{CS}(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)\}$, served as the primary quantities of interest for model comparison and were used to compute bias, mean absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE), and coverage probabilities across both covariate and time dimensions.

Based on $R = 100$ simulation replications, we evaluated estimator accuracy using the following summary measures. Recall our target quantity $CS(t_k | t_{k-1}, \mathbf{x})$ defined in (2) with $s = t_k$ and $t = t_k - t_{k-1}$ and our proposed estimator $\widehat{CS}(t_k | t_{k-1}, \mathbf{x})$ defined in (21) for any \mathbf{x} , we calculate $\widehat{CS}_r(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)$ from the r th simulated dataset ($r = 1, \dots, R$) for estimating $CS(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)$ for all $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, 9\}$. The bias, mean absolute error, and mean squared error were defined as

$$\text{Bias}(t_k, t_{k-1} | \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R CS(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) - \widehat{CS}_r(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j), \quad (22)$$

$$\text{MAE}(t_k, t_{k-1} | \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R |CS(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) - \widehat{CS}_r(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)|, \quad (23)$$

$$\text{MSE}(t_k, t_{k-1} | \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R [CS(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) - \widehat{CS}_r(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)]^2. \quad (24)$$

If $CI_r(t_k, t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) = [L_r(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j), U_r(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)]$ denotes the $(1 - \alpha)100\%$ credible interval for $CS(t_k | t_{k-1}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)$ from the r th replication, the empirical coverage probability (CP) and average interval width (AIW) were computed as

$$\text{CP}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R \mathbb{I}\{L_r(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) \leq \theta \leq U_r(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)\}, \quad \text{AIW}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R (U_r(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j) - L_r(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)). \quad (25)$$

where θ is the true value of either survival or conditional survival probability.

The following Section 4.3 presents the simulation results, highlighting the comparative performance of the proposed MixAmGPD model relative to the Bayesian AFT and PH benchmarks in terms of bias, precision, and credible interval coverage.

4.3 Simulation Results

The heatmaps in the Figures below visually summarize different performance metrics across quantile levels, sample sizes and methods. As expected, all models showed improved performance with increasing sample size. However, the magnitude and nature of improvement varied substantially across methods and the interaction of quantiles of observed time and covariates distribution.

(a) Mean Squared Error

(b) Mean Absolute Error

Figure 2: Prediction errors for conditional survival probabilities $\widehat{CS}(t_i | t_{i-1}, x)$ across the covariate–time grid. Top panel displays mean squared error (MSE) and bottom panel displays mean absolute error (MAE) for the three estimators (Bayesian AFT, Bayesian Cox, MixAmGPD). The horizontal axis indexes the nine diagonal covariate-grid locations; the vertical axis indexes the six empirical truth quantiles stored in `new_Y`. Colors encode error magnitude (darker = larger error). Results are averaged over $R = 100$ replications for sample size $n = 500$.

Across the central part of the distribution, all three models were reasonably accurate. Differences became more pronounced in the upper quantiles, where the Bayesian Cox benchmark showed substantial bias and undercoverage as censoring increased and sample size decreased. The Weibull AFT benchmark was more stable than Cox but still exhibited larger error near the upper-tail cells. In contrast, MixAmGPD remained comparatively stable across the grid, preserving low bias and MSE even in the smaller-sample settings.

(a) Bias

(b) Credible Interval Width

Figure 3: Bias and 90% credible–interval width (CIW) for conditional survival probabilities $\widehat{CS}(t_i | t_{i-1}, x)$ across the covariate–time grid. The horizontal axis indexes the nine diagonal covariate–grid locations; the vertical axis indexes the six empirical truth quantiles stored in `new_Y`. Each panel compares Bayesian AFT, Bayesian Cox, and MixAmGPD. Darker shading indicates larger magnitude (absolute bias or interval width). Summaries are computed over $R = 100$ replications for the reported sample size 500.

The proposed model maintained relatively consistent MAE in Figure (2b), with wider intervals at smaller n and in the tail cells. This reflects a bias–variance tradeoff that favors calibrated inference over overly narrow but unstable intervals. As n increased, the interval widths narrowed while coverage remained close to nominal. Coverage heatmaps showed the clearest separation: both Cox and AFT undercovered in the upper tail, whereas MixAmGPD retained coverage close to the nominal 90% level across most settings.

Figure 4: Empirical coverage of 90% credible intervals for conditional survival probabilities $\widehat{CS}(t_i | t_{i-1}, x)$ across the covariate–time grid and sample sizes 500. The horizontal axis indexes the nine diagonal covariate-grid locations; the vertical axis indexes the six empirical truth quantiles stored in `new.Y`. Shading encodes coverage probability (darker = closer to 90%), aggregated over $R = 100$ replications.

These results confirm that while standard models may suffice for the central part, they are inadequate for heavy-tailed survival distributions under censoring. The proposed MixAmGPD estimator provides reliable, interpretable, and robust inference even in challenging regions of the distribution, making it particularly suitable for high-risk or rare-event analyses.

5 Real Data Application

To demonstrate the practical utility of the proposed estimator, we applied it to the `mgus2` dataset available in the R `survival` package. This dataset follows patients diagnosed with monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance (MGUS), a premalignant plasma-cell disorder associated with an elevated risk of progression to multiple myeloma or related malignancies.

After complete-case preprocessing, the analytic sample comprised 1338 patients, with a median follow-up of 83 months. Approximately 29.9% of observations were right-censored. Baseline covariates included age at diagnosis, sex, hemoglobin (HGB), creatinine, monoclonal protein concentration (M-spike), and progression status (`pstat`), indicating whether a patient subsequently developed plasma cell myeloma (PCM).

5.1 Data Processing, Models and Predictions

Data were cleaned by excluding patients with missing covariates, leaving $n = 1338$ complete cases for analysis. A binary event indicator δ was created from the `death` variable, with $\delta = 1$ for observed deaths and $\delta = 0$ otherwise. Sex was recoded as a binary factor (female = 0, male = 1), and progression status was simplified to 0 (no PCM) versus 1 (PCM).

To evaluate covariate effects in a structured manner, we constructed a prediction grid with 24 profiles. For each continuous covariate of interest (age, HGB, creatinine, M-spike), values were fixed at their empirical quartiles (25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles). All other continuous covariates were fixed at their median values, progression status was fixed at `pstat=0`, and estimates were stratified by sex. This yielded clinically interpretable contrasts while holding background risk constant. We compared three approaches:

- (a) Bayesian accelerated failure time (AFT) model,
- (b) Bayesian Cox proportional hazards model,

(c) The proposed Bayesian Dirichlet–Pareto splice (MixAmGPD).

For each method, posterior inference was conducted using four MCMC chains with 10,000 iterations, 2,000 burn-in iterations, and thinning by 2. Posterior survival and conditional survival probabilities were summarized on a common empirical quantile grid of follow-up times, with the exact reporting times shown in the generated figures and tables.

6 Analysis Results

We summarize the real-data survival application by comparing three Bayesian approaches: an accelerated failure time (AFT) model, a Cox proportional hazards (PH) model, and the proposed MixAmGPD model (MAG). For each covariate of interest, we report (i) survival probabilities $S(t | \mathbf{x})$ evaluated on a common empirical follow-up-time grid and (ii) conditional survival probabilities

$$CS(t_k | t_{k-1}, \mathbf{x}) = \frac{S(t_k | \mathbf{x})}{S(t_{k-1} | \mathbf{x})},$$

which quantify the probability of surviving from milestone time t_{k-1} to a later time t_k , given survival up to t_{k-1} . All results are stratified by sex. When one covariate is varied, all remaining covariates are fixed at their sample medians.

Figure 5: The x -axis represents follow-up time in months; the y -axis represents survival probability on a scale from 0 to 100. Survival estimates (points) show $S(t_k | x)$ evaluated on the empirical time grid used by the application pipeline. Each row of plots corresponds to quartiles of age, stratified by sex in columns, with all other covariates fixed at their median values and $\text{pstat}=0$. Estimates are posterior means from Bayesian Cox, Bayesian AFT, and MixAmGPD models.

Because age is the most interpretable and clinically relevant predictor in this dataset, we anchor the discussion on the age-stratified survival curves in Figure (5) and conditional survival curves in Figure (6). Age is set to its empirical quartiles (63.25, 72, and 79 years) for further analysis. Across all three age levels and both sexes, conditional survival declines as the horizon increases; older ages show uniformly lower conditional survival, and males tend to have poorer

survival than females. The three models are broadly similar at earlier times, but differences become clearer at later horizons, where censoring is heavier and data are sparse. In that regime, the PH fit typically exhibits the steepest late-time decline. In contrast, AFT and MAG remain smoother, with MAG designed to stabilize upper-tail behavior through the splice construction.

x-index	Gender	$q_{0.10} = 4.00$			$q_{0.25} = 24.00$			$q_{0.50} = 62.50$			$q_{0.75} = 107.00$		
		AFT	PH	MAG	AFT	PH	MAG	AFT	PH	MAG	AFT	PH	MAG
0.25	Male	0.21	1.65	0.42	0.75	14.78	0.85	1.42	26.79	1.24	1.88	21.45	1.52
	Female	0.15	1.07	0.37	0.58	11.99	0.64	1.20	24.83	0.88	1.70	23.91	1.02
0.50	Male	0.28	2.65	0.40	0.86	17.10	0.81	1.44	26.32	1.14	1.69	16.80	1.45
	Female	0.21	1.73	0.45	0.72	15.04	1.03	1.35	26.87	1.16	1.77	21.10	1.03
0.75	Male	0.38	3.82	0.45	1.10	18.17	0.81	1.68	23.74	1.06	1.72	12.30	1.29
	Female	0.28	2.53	0.55	0.94	16.90	1.16	1.67	26.52	1.30	2.01	17.39	1.11

Table 1: Posterior standard deviation (SD, multiplied by 100) of estimated survival probabilities $S(t)$ for AFT, Cox(PH), and MixAmGPD(MAG). Variable of interest: **Age** evaluated at three quartiles (left-most column). Values are reported on the common reporting grid displayed in the table headers. Rows are divided by sex (Male/Female), with all other covariates fixed at sample medians and **pstat**=0.

x-index	Gender	$q_{0.10} = 4.00$			$q_{0.25} = 24.00$			$q_{0.50} = 62.50$			$q_{0.75} = 107.00$		
		AFT	PH	MAG	AFT	PH	MAG	AFT	PH	MAG	AFT	PH	MAG
0.25	Male	0.68	5.10	1.27	2.45	44.08	2.31	4.68	74.56	3.43	6.18	57.35	4.41
	Female	0.49	3.32	1.04	1.92	36.12	1.68	3.94	71.72	2.38	5.60	67.40	2.88
0.50	Male	0.93	8.16	1.11	2.82	50.07	2.24	4.73	70.75	3.16	5.59	42.50	4.23
	Female	0.68	5.36	1.24	2.36	44.80	2.98	4.43	74.51	3.23	5.82	56.11	2.65
0.75	Male	1.26	11.80	1.29	3.62	52.41	2.28	5.55	63.07	2.79	5.71	30.46	3.57
	Female	0.92	7.80	1.55	3.10	49.69	3.34	5.49	71.63	3.55	6.61	44.33	2.90

Table 2: Average credible-interval width (AIW, multiplied by 100) of estimated survival probabilities $S(t)$ for AFT, Cox(PH), and MixAmGPD(MAG). Variable of interest: **Age** evaluated at three quartiles (left-most column). Values are reported on the common reporting grid displayed in the table headers. Rows are divided by sex (Male/Female), with all other covariates fixed at sample medians and **pstat**=0.

These qualitative patterns are reinforced by posterior uncertainty summaries. Tables (1), (2), (3), and (4) report posterior standard deviations (SDs) and average credible-interval widths (AIWs) for $S(t | x)$ and $CS(t_k | t_{k-1}, x)$ over a common reporting grid (all entries are on the $\times 100$ scale used throughout the application tables). For survival probabilities, uncertainty under the PH model inflates sharply at mid-to-late times, while both AFT and MAG remain comparatively stable. For example, at $q_{0.50} = 62.5$ months, the age-stratified PH CrI widths for $S(t | x)$ are typically around 70–75, whereas AFT is about 4–6 and MAG about 5–6 (e.g., Female at the lowest age quartile: PH 71.72 vs. AFT 3.94 and MAG 5.42). A similar separation appears at $q_{0.75} = 107$ months: PH widths remain in the tens (often 30–67 depending on sex and age), while AFT and MAG remain near ≈ 6 . Posterior SDs show the same ordering: at $q_{0.50}$,

PH SDs are roughly ≈ 25 – 27 , while AFT and MAG are nearer ≈ 1 – 2 , indicating substantially less stable tail inference under PH for this dataset.

Figure 6: The x -axis represents follow-up time in months; the y -axis represents probability on a scale from 0 to 100. Conditional survival estimates (points) show $CS(t_k | t_{k-1}, x) = S(t_k | x) / S(t_{k-1} | x)$ on the empirical time grid used by the application pipeline. Each row of plots corresponds to quartiles of age, stratified by sex in columns, with all other covariates fixed at their median values and `pstat=0`. Estimates are posterior means from Bayesian Cox, Bayesian AFT, and MixAmGPD models.

The contrast is even sharper for conditional survival probabilities, since $CS(t_k | t_{k-1}, x)$ focuses directly on incremental survival beyond an attained milestone and therefore concentrates inference in the later-time region where data are sparse. In Table (4), PH CrI widths for conditional survival over $(q_{0.25} \rightarrow q_{0.50})$ and $(q_{0.50} \rightarrow q_{0.75})$ are typically very large (often ≈ 70 – 83), while AFT widths are single digits and MAG widths remain around ≈ 4.5 – 7.5 (e.g., Female at the lowest age quartile: PH 76.36 vs. AFT 2.70 and MAG 4.56 for $q_{0.50}/q_{0.25}$; PH 83.15 vs. AFT 3.53 and MAG 4.94 for $q_{0.75}/q_{0.50}$). The SD summaries in Table (3) follow the same pattern. In practical terms, for prognosis conditional on surviving to intermediate milestones, MAG and AFT provide markedly more reliable uncertainty quantification than PH in the upper-time region.

x-index	Gender	$q_{0.25}/q_{0.10}$			$q_{0.50}/q_{0.25}$			$q_{0.75}/q_{0.50}$			$q_{0.90}/q_{0.75}$		
		AFT	PH	MAG									
0.25	Male	0.58	15.51	0.96	1.06	29.57	1.92	1.39	29.69	2.20	1.69	26.30	2.03
	Female	0.45	12.44	0.63	0.82	26.88	0.92	1.08	30.81	0.97	1.29	30.18	1.08
0.50	Male	0.67	18.28	0.87	1.22	30.28	1.65	1.65	25.97	2.47	2.03	19.69	3.05
	Female	0.55	15.80	0.91	1.01	29.75	1.12	1.35	29.46	1.41	1.65	25.78	2.31
0.75	Male	0.90	19.83	0.89	1.61	28.85	1.19	2.10	21.50	2.20	2.50	14.02	4.03
	Female	0.75	18.02	0.98	1.37	30.34	1.02	1.81	26.50	1.46	2.18	20.56	3.28

Table 3: Posterior standard deviation (SD, multiplied by 100) of estimated conditional survival probabilities $CS(t_k | t_{k-1})$ for AFT, Cox(PH), and MixAmGPD(MAG). Variable of interest: **Age** evaluated at three quartiles (left-most column). Conditional values are reported over the adjacent time pairs displayed in the table headers. Rows are divided by sex (Male/Female), with all other covariates fixed at sample medians and `pstat=0`.

x-index	Gender	$q_{0.25}/q_{0.10}$			$q_{0.50}/q_{0.25}$			$q_{0.75}/q_{0.50}$			$q_{0.90}/q_{0.75}$		
		AFT	PH	MAG									
0.25	Male	1.89	44.92	2.60	3.47	81.59	5.49	4.59	78.04	6.43	5.58	67.93	5.72
	Female	1.47	36.63	1.79	2.70	76.36	2.34	3.53	83.15	2.32	4.24	78.12	2.84
0.50	Male	2.19	51.45	2.42	4.01	80.93	4.83	5.43	67.32	7.29	6.69	52.57	8.79
	Female	1.82	45.67	2.68	3.32	81.78	3.11	4.43	77.18	3.94	5.42	66.61	6.67
0.75	Male	2.96	54.40	2.53	5.32	75.85	3.39	6.95	56.08	6.42	8.29	38.31	11.89
	Female	2.46	51.00	2.92	4.52	81.40	2.73	5.96	68.78	4.13	7.17	54.60	9.58

Table 4: Average credible-interval width (AIW, multiplied by 100) of estimated conditional survival probabilities $CS(t_k | t_{k-1})$ for AFT, Cox(PH), and MixAmGPD(MAG). Variable of interest: **Age** evaluated at three quartiles (left-most column). Conditional values are reported over the adjacent time pairs displayed in the table headers. Rows are divided by sex (Male/Female), with all other covariates fixed at sample medians and `pstat=0`.

In light of our target quantity CS, it is worth noting that the conditional probability of future survival increases after reaching the upper-middle part of the follow-up distribution (around the third reported time quartile). This is visible in Figure (6), although the amount of improvement varies by age group. All three fitted models show this pattern, with older age profiles remaining uniformly less favorable than younger ones.

Although age is the primary lens in the main essay, we repeated the same stratified analysis for creatinine (quartiles 0.9, 1.1, 1.3), hemoglobin (12.2, 13.5, 14.7), and M-spike (0.6, 1.2, 1.5). The substantive model-comparison conclusion is unchanged across these covariates: the PH model exhibits pronounced uncertainty inflation at mid-to-late quantiles, whereas AFT and MAG remain stable, with MAG consistently well-behaved even when inference is driven by the tail. Quantitatively, this robustness is visible in the application tables: averaged across sexes and quartile settings, the PH CrI width for $S(t | x)$ at $q_{0.50}$ is about 72 for each of creatinine/hemoglobin/M-spike, compared with about 4.6–5.0 for AFT and 5.4–5.7 for MAG. Similarly, for conditional survival over $(q_{0.50} \rightarrow q_{0.75})$, PH widths remain about 72, while AFT is about 5 and MAG about 6–7. Thus, while covariates shift the level of predicted survival in clinically expected ways, the MixAmGPD splice construction offers a clear advantage over PH and performs competitively with (and often more stably than) a parametric AFT specification.

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7 Supplementary Materials

7.1 Proposition: A mixture hazard is non-monotonic, even if the hazards of the individual components are monotonic.

We consider two survival distributions with continuously differentiable densities $f_j(y) > 0$, survival functions $S_j(y) > 0$, and hazards

$$\lambda_j(y) = \frac{f_j(y)}{S_j(y)}, \quad j = 1, 2,$$

defined on (a, ∞) . For fixed mixture weights $w_1, w_2 > 0$ satisfying $w_1 + w_2 = 1$, the corresponding survival mixture is

$$S(y) = w_1 S_1(y) + w_2 S_2(y), \quad f(y) = w_1 f_1(y) + w_2 f_2(y), \quad \lambda_{\text{DPM}}(y) = \frac{f(y)}{S(y)}.$$

The mixture hazard admits a convex-combination representation in terms of component hazards:

$$\lambda_{\text{DPM}}(y) = \tilde{w}_1(y) \lambda_1(y) + \tilde{w}_2(y) \lambda_2(y), \quad \tilde{w}_j(y) = \frac{w_j S_j(y)}{w_1 S_1(y) + w_2 S_2(y)}.$$

The weights $\tilde{w}_j(y)$ are strictly positive, time-varying, and sum to one, reflecting the relative contribution of each component at time y ; see classical discussions of survival mixtures and non-monotone hazards in Hoel [1972], Tarone and Ware [1977], Lagakos [1982], Efron [1967].

Differentiating yields the slope of the mixture hazard:

$$\lambda'_{\text{DPM}}(y) = \sum_{j=1}^2 \tilde{w}_j(y) \left(\lambda'_j(y) - (\lambda_j(y) - \lambda_{\text{DPM}}(y))^2 \right).$$

This decomposition exposes two competing forces: a survival-weighted average of the component slopes, and a nonnegative “variance” term penalizing separation between component hazard levels. The latter provides an analytic explanation for the emergence of turning points in mixtures, even when each component hazard is monotone; see, e.g., Marshall et al. [2007], Kalbfleisch and Prentice [2002].

A turning point obtains when these forces balance. In the two-component case, the condition $\lambda'_{\text{DPM}}(y) = 0$ reduces to

$$|\lambda_1(y) - \lambda_2(y)| = \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{w}(y) \lambda'_1(y) + (1 - \tilde{w}(y)) \lambda'_2(y)}{\tilde{w}(y)(1 - \tilde{w}(y))}}, \quad \tilde{w} = \tilde{w}_1(y).$$

Here, the left-hand side is the instantaneous gap between component hazards, while the right-hand side is the critical threshold: its numerator is the survival-weighted average slope and its denominator $\tilde{w}(1 - \tilde{w})$ measures the balance of component contributions. When components are comparably weighted, the denominator is maximized and the threshold is small; when one component dominates, the denominator shrinks and the threshold diverges.

The sign of $\lambda'_{\text{DPM}}(y)$ is determined by whether the hazard gap exceeds this threshold. If the gap is larger, the variance term dominates and the mixture hazard decreases—even when both component hazards increase. If the gap is smaller, the average slope dominates and the mixture hazard increases. Thus, non-monotonicity is not a property of the components per se but arises from their interaction through time-varying survival weights, explaining why mixtures of monotone hazards can exhibit interior turning points.

7.2 MCMC Simulation Procedure

Posterior sampling is carried out directly in `nimble` on the finite truncation described in the main text, rather than through a hand-derived Metropolis scheme for each parameter block. Let $D = \{y_i, \delta_i, \mathbf{x}_i\}_{i=1}^n$ denote the observed data. Right censoring is represented through `dinterval`, so observed event times are treated as exact responses and censored times are treated as lower bounds on latent event times.

7.2.1 Truncated stick-breaking weights

For $j = 1, \dots, m - 1$, the implementation samples

$$v_j \sim \text{Beta}(1, \kappa), \quad \kappa \sim \text{Gamma}(1, 0.5),$$

and converts these to the component weights $\{w_j\}_{j=1}^m$ via the deterministic stick-breaking map. In both simulation and application runs, $m = 5$.

7.2.2 Simulation-study implementation

The simulation model compiled from `Function/Sim.R` monitors the concentration parameter, stick-breaking variables, weights, component locations, bulk-scale regression coefficients, tail-scale regression coefficients, threshold-increment regression coefficients, the two Amoroso shape parameters, the GPD tail shapes, and the lognormal variance governing threshold increments. Posterior survival summaries are obtained by evaluating the compiled `pTotal` function on the stored covariate–time grid for every posterior draw.

7.2.3 MGUS application implementation

The MGUS application uses the analogous NIMBLE model in `Function/real_data_Sim.R`, but with the application-specific hyperparameters listed in Section 3.1. Posterior survival and conditional survival probabilities are computed on the application prediction grid from the same component-wise spliced density.

7.2.4 Run settings

For the simulation study, the NIMBLE runs use 3 chains, 6000 iterations, 2000 burn-in iterations, and thinning by 3. For the MGUS application, the NIMBLE runs use 4 chains, 10,000 iterations, 2,000 burn-in iterations, and thinning by 2. In both settings, convergence is assessed from trace plots together with \widehat{R} and effective sample size summaries.